

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF SYNCRETISM IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: Language is the most significant and remarkably flawless means of human communication, a way of sharing thoughts, capable of performing these numerous and complicated activities due to its extremely flexible and ordered system. Language observations demonstrate that transitory occurrences affect the liveliness of language and the dynamic aspect of its evolution. This article discusses specific features of syncretism in English and Uzbek languages.

Key words: syncretism, structure, cognition, resource, linguistic theories mastery.

Аннотация: Язык — важнейшее и удивительно безупречное средство человеческого общения, способ обмена мыслями, способный осуществлять эти многочисленные и сложные виды деятельности благодаря своей чрезвычайно гибкой и упорядоченной системе. Наблюдения за языком показывают, что преходящие события влияют на живость языка и динамический аспект его эволюции. В данной статье рассматриваются особенности синкретизма в английском и узбекском языках.

Ключевые слова: синкретизм, структура, познание, ресурс, освоение лингвистических теорий.

Annotasiya: Til insoniy muloqotning eng muhim va hayratlanarli darajada benuqson vositasi, fikr almashish usuli bo'lib, o'zining nihoyatda moslashuvchan va tartibli tizimi tufayli ana shunday ko'p va murakkab faoliyat turlarini amalga oshirishga qodir. Tilning kuzatuvlari shuni ko'rsatadiki, o'tkinchi hodisalar tilning hayotiylikiga va uning rivojlanishining dinamik tomoniga ta'sir qiladi. Ushbu maqolada ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi sinkretizmning xususiyatlari muhokama qilinadi.

Tayanch so'zlar: sinkretizm, struktura, idrok, resurs, lingvistik nazariyalarni o'zlashtirish.

Modern linguistic theories based on structural descriptions of language are increasingly turning to the study of phenomena that extend beyond the strict limits of even the most detailed classifications and are distinguished by the lack of a complete set of differential features of any one grammatical category. Natural language must be a self-sufficient system in all types and spheres of speech activity in order to function effectively; thus, processes of constant development, enrichment, and improvement of its resources and expressive and visual means are an integral part of the language's functional life. They span all of its levels, however the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of the degree of influence on multi-level units, the intensity, and pace

of systemic structural changes in language subsystems varied. Various aspects of syncretism in the grammar of English, Russian, German and other languages have been studied in the works of such scientists as J.L. Elmslev (1960), V.V. Vinogradov (1978), S. Bally (2001), O. Espersen (1958), V.V. Babaytseva (1967, 1973), V. Skalichka (1967), V.V. Buzarov (1998, 2001), M. Aronoff (1994), S.N. Daniel (1999), T. Petterson (1988), J.P. Blevins (1995), V. Bloch (1966), A. Calabrese (1995). There are many works devoted to the description of the essence, nature and typology of syncretism (V.V. Babaytseva (2000), I.V. Vysotskaya (2006), G. Meiser (1992), S. Luraghi (1987), J. Johnston (1997), M. Wheeler (1993)). In many modern works, scientists describe the characteristic features of the manifestation of syncretism at the syntactic level (N.A. Kobrina (2007), T.E. Anoshkina (1981), V.V. Babaytseva (1984, 1997), Z.V. Valyusinskaya (1992), P.V. Chesnokov (1992), L.D. Chesnokova (1988), L.L. Bezobrazova (1993)). The largest number of studies is devoted to the description of syncretism of case forms (V. Milan (1988), T. Petterson (1988)). There are several perspectives in general linguistics and Turkology on the evolution and formation of cognate terms. Since ancient times, these perspectives on linguistic facts have been examined using morphological laws of languages.

V.V. Vinogradov, a Russian linguist, also observed that nouns and verbs in a language are composed of pairs with the same phonetic structure, noting that "...the verb system is more syncretic and syntactic than all independent word groups¹". Turkologist E.V. Sevortyan has the same viewpoint. He goes on to state, "... the initial verb formation consists of a verb and a noun core, and differs only in the text."

Many linguists have worked to determine the essence, nature, and nature of syncretism as a phenomena, researching its various manifestations. Nonetheless, Russian linguistics is distinguished by a change in focus toward the study of syncretism at the syntax level, whereas international experts are more concerned with concerns of syncretism expression at the morphological level. A systematic grammar method has long been dominant in the study of syncretic events. The phenomena of syncretism reflects the interdependence of morphology and syntax. The ambiguity of the idea itself, as well as the lack of a uniform language, is one of the challenges emerging from the uncertainty of linguistic views surrounding the question of the objective substance of the concept of syncretism. The growth of Manfred Bierwisch's theories resulted in a new approach in the understanding of syncretism. In his paper "Syntactic features in

morphology: general problems of the so-called system of nominative endings in the German language," assumptions regarding a particular system of links between the levels of morphology and syntax were established, which is represented in the phenomena of syncretism. The necessity to distinguish syncretism and similar phenomena is the most contentious problem (I.V. Artyushkov, A.Ya. Bauder, K.E. Stein). Studies on the subject of the link between syncretism and cognitive mechanisms (L.S. Vygotsky) should also be considered. A new interpretation of syncretism from the perspective of cognitive grammar (considering the meaningful means by which the speech-thinking processes of speech generation and understanding are verbalized) contributes to the deepening of our understanding of language's hidden mechanisms.

The process of evolution and renewal of diverse expressive methods is unending in diachronic terms. If a language works continually and serves all of society's major communication realms, it is potentially limitless in terms of its ability to be consistently updated and evolve spontaneously. The language, on the other hand, should not be an arch-complex education, extravagant in resources and limitless in cognition and mastery. G. Paul said in his book "Principles of the History of Language" that "in general, language activity is characterized by a certain thriftiness." According to this pattern, the language creates expressions for all circumstances that contain only what is required for comprehension.

The number of ways employed is determined by the situation, the context of the speech, and the degree of similarity in the spiritual stock of the speakers" (Paul 1960: 372). Furthermore, "the richness of language forms, especially the rules of their use, is limited by the amount of memory of people for whom language is primarily a means of communication and thought transmission" (Kodukhov 1974: 201). As a result, the language serves as a mechanism for not only updating, multiplying, and increasing its resources, but also for conserving, compressing, and optimizing expressive methods in all of its subsystems.

However, it appears to us that the problems of linguistic economy proper in modern linguistics are on the periphery due to the narrowing of the theoretical and factual basis of this phenomenon, the latter being absent from the range of issues subject to mandatory consideration when describing any particular language. Syncretism is one of the special cases of linguistic economy implementation observed at various levels of the language system. It is defined as "the combination (synthesis)

of differential structural and semantic features of language units (some categories of words, meanings, sentences, sentence members, etc.) opposed to each other in the language system and related transitivity phenomena."

These are all hybrid forms (contamination, intermediate, diffuse)." Syncretic phenomena in English have so far been studied only within the context of morphology, despite the fact that they represent the linguistic reality of the interaction of the levels of morphology and syntax, and thus their analysis is required for a more complete and in-depth description of the language system and its functioning. Furthermore, as N.A. Kudrina points out, "such units are typical of any language and all language levels".

Despite the large amount of literature on this topic, syncretism constantly attracts the attention of research and at present, its complex functional analysis at the level of morphology and syntax remains an urgent research direction. Such a dynamic phenomenon as syncretism is not given enough attention both in general and in particular linguistics, therefore, in our dissertation research, an attempt is made to comprehensively study the features of the manifestation of syncretism at the level of morphology and syntax of the English language, which it acquires at these levels as a means of linguistic economy.

To conclude we may say that the study of syncretism as a multidimensional phenomenon has once again demonstrated that this issue has not yet been thoroughly researched; there are many unanswered concerns regarding syncretic phenomena at the textual level, its tender aspects, and syncretistic style elements. All of these topics require their own investigation.

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